

ONTOGENY OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Problems that may arise during the development of speech may occur in each person. Ontogeny of speech development is described in detail in this article.

Currently, various disciplines are paying attention to the study of speech: psychology, speech therapy, physiology, psychoacoustics, medicine, pedagogy. In this line, psychology stands out as the main science in its systematic relationship with several mentioned fields and in this problem of science. Because he is responsible for a set of problems related to children's speech, understanding the nature of speech-language ability, its development and activity. The topic of children's first speech has a great place in world psychology today. In many countries, there are strong research teams that study the development of children's speech, international cooperation of experts is increasing, books and journals are published in collaboration with psychologists from different countries (USA, Germany, Italy, Finland, Russia), new issues are developments are proposed. Speech ontogenesis - speech formation and development of a person from birth to the end of his life. The main goal of the science is to develop a system aimed at predicting the child's speech development in normal and disturbed ontogeny, as well as to prevent speech defects. The task of science is to study the ontogenesis of speech activity in various forms of its components.

- a) study of normal and pathological speech development processes in children.
- b) to determine the conditions and factors that develop speech.
- c) study the periodicity of the development of human speech and modern concepts.
- d) formation of understanding of individual and age characteristics of normal and pathological speech development in children.
- e) determination of the content and tasks of working with normal and ontogeny-disordered children in a group of children and individually.
- f) improvement of speech disorder prevention methods

It is a problem about the relation of genetic and social factors in the development of speech. Within this problem is the task of determining how speech and language are influenced by genetic factors, because speech is a product of social influence. Solving this problem is very

important not only from a theoretical point of view, but also from a practical point of view. In the 20th century, a theory about the development of children's speech called "social model" appeared. According to this theory, the child's speech is realized due to the acquisition of the language of those around him, as well as through the collective actions of the society. One of his main views is that the child begins to speak the language he hears around him. Today, there is a lot of information about the influence of genetic factors on the development of human speech. Two factors lead to this conclusion. This is the result of psychogenetic research in the study of human speech language abilities and the process of studying speech ontogeny. Psychogenetic studies provide us with information about the transmission of a number of speech signs from generation to generation. Therefore, in order to study the genetic components of language, the linguistic abilities of adopted children were compared with those of their biological and adoptive parents. It was found that genetic factors are much stronger than the environment. Mechanisms of various language disorders are inherited. For example, in the family, the grandmother passed her speech problem to four of her five children, and in turn, 11 of her 23 grandchildren have the same defect. Dyslexia has been observed. It is characterized by the fact that even mentally healthy people have difficulty reading written words, and dyslexia in various forms ranges from 5-30% of the human population. Research shows that dyslexia runs in families: at least one family member is usually dyslexic. Genetic factors have also been identified in other forms of speech activity in humans. The effects of genetic factors can also be found in the study of speech ontogeny. They are manifested in the spontaneity of activities and the independent development of some pre-speech events in the child's pre-speech period.

The central speech apparatus is located in the brain. It consists of the cerebral cortex, subcortical nodes, conduction pathways, core (primarily in the medulla oblongata), nuclei, and nerves that go to the muscles of voice, breathing, and articulation. The function of the central speech department is that speech, like other forms of higher nervous activity, is formed on the basis of reflexes. Speech reflexes are related to the activity of different parts of the brain. However, some parts of the cerebral cortex play a key role in the formation of speech. These are the forehead, temple and nape of the left (right in Chapakay) hemi-sha. An active participant in speech activity in these parts of the cerebral cortex:

- speech movement analyzer;
- speech vision analyzer;
- speech analyzer is located.

The speech-action analyzer is located in the left frontal part of the cerebral cortex and is called Broca's center. This part participates in the emergence of oral speech. The speech auditory analyzer is located in the left temporal part of the cerebral cortex and is called Wernicke's center. In this part, the process of receiving foreign speech takes place. The posterior lobe of the cerebral cortex plays a major role in understanding speech. It is considered the visual center of the brain and serves to master written speech. Subcortical nuclei control the speed and expressiveness of speech. Speech is a higher mental function, which integrates many functional systems. Speech development in infants during the first months after birth is ensured by the innate hearing and emerging ability to fix the gaze on the face of an adult. Innate emotional reactions are also being developed during this period, turning into nonverbal forms of communication. At about 6 months a baby starts to pronounce some

syllables; at 7–9 months – repeats various sounds combinations, pronounced by adults. At 10–11 months a baby begins to react on the words, referred to him/her. The first words usually appear at an age of 1 year; this is the start of the stage of active speech development. At this time it is acceptable, if a child confuses or rearranges sounds, distorts or misses them. By the age of 1.5 years a child begins to understand abstract explanations of adults. Significant vocabulary enlargement occurs between 2 and 3 years; grammatical structures of the language are being formed during this period (a child starts to use phrases and sentences). Preschool age (3–7 y. o.) is characterized by incorrect, but steadily improving pronunciation of sounds and phonemic perception. The vocabulary increases; abstract speech and retelling are being formed. Children over 7 y. o. continue to improve grammar, writing and reading skills. The described stages may not have strict age boundaries, as soon as they are dependent not only on environment, but also on the child's mental constitution, heredity and character.

The development of active speech of the child, performing the signal-sign function, begins with one-word statements, with the stage of individual words-sentences. According to the latest research, the content of the first word-sentences refers to a holistic situation, and from the form they are merged in an indissoluble unity of subject and predicate, nomination and predication, elements of semantics, grammar and syntax. There's no partition of a situation, no partition of a speech form. At the same time, it is recognized that the first one word sentences contain the rudiments of everything that a child has to develop when learning an adult language, that a one-word sentence is an initial instruction in many respects. Leading activity of the child at the age from 1 year to 3 years -mastering subject and of the operating side of the business, i.e., acquaintance with surrounding objects and the appropriation of public-developed ways to use them. In joint activities, the function of indicating and designating the subject of the word is strengthened. Further development of the function of naming objects is determined by the cooperation with an adult. For the formation and development of grammatical meaning, the mechanism of not imitation, but the need for speech communication should operate. Grammatical meanings are the meanings of relations between the phenomena of reality indicated by words, i.e. they are the linguistic meanings of the logical (mental) series. There are grammatical meanings of word-formative morphemes and grammatical meanings in syntax. To understand speech, it is not enough to know the lexical meaning of the words it consists of, it is necessary to understand the meaning of grammatical forms used in the communication process.

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